

THE MANAGEMENT OF SPORTS RESOURCES IN HOCHIMINH NATIONAL UNIVERSITY, VIETNAM

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Abstract:

Governance plays a very important role in most social organizations. For any organization, company, or a country, a community, the role of governance becomes more important than ever. For schools, the term management is somewhat strange to some people, especially the term "sports management", which attracts little interest from the leadership. But sport in school is also one of the school's organizations to meet the goal of comprehensive human education. Therefore, the organization of the school requires good governance and management, which is considered to be an essential part to the success of education. Good governance will help the physical training and sport activities to improve the quality of physical training and sports, enhance the movement of physical training and sports activities and especially find the sports talent for the country.

Keywords: management of sports resources, Hochiminh National University, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Man is the force of development of a nation's construction, the subject of all creativity, the subject of all material and cultural goods, the subject to build a fair and loving society. Thus, human beings need to develop comprehensively, develop intellectually, have physical strength, mentality and virtue. *"Sport development is an important part of the socio-economic development policy of the Party and the State to foster and promote the human factor. Sports and physical training activities must contribute to improve the health, physical strength, moral education, healthy lifestyles, enriching the spiritual and cultural life of the people and raising social labor productivity."* [1].

And *"Promote physical activities, sports in both size and quality. Encourage and create conditions for every people to participate in activities and develop physical training and sports. Promote mass sports, amateur sports, first of all, in adolescence. Increase physical education in school"* [2].

In the development strategy of Vietnam National University in Hochiminh City (in the period of 2011- 2015), with a vision to 2020. Among the strategy group, there are 5 strategies mentioning "*Improving the efficiency of system-wide governance*" , affirmed: "*VNU-HCM (Vietnam National University in Hochiminh City) with a strong and professional management staff, operated under the advanced management model, in accordance with the trend of developing universities in the world.*" It also gives out the aim that "in the period of 2015-2015, VNU-HCM is a center of training, scientific research and technology transfer of multi-field, multi-major, high quality leading and core in the system of higher education in Vietnam with some regional-standard and international-standard training programmes... ". Subsequently, in the development strategy of VNU-HCM in the period 2015-2020, in the strategy group 3 on training quality, "*VNU-HCM builds a leading quality training system in Asia,, helping learners to develop comprehensively and maximize their potential. Improve the quality of training in the direction of meeting the increasing demand for social and international integration.*" To achieve these goals comprehensively, the contribution of sport and physical training plays an important part. Sport and physical training is the basic factor for the fast and sustainable development of the physical training and sport movement as well as contributing to the high quality labor force of VNU-HCM in particular and the country in general.

In fact, in recent years, all departments and schools in VNU-HCM have implemented many models of sports clubs, student teams, teachers team to participate in the national and international tournament. In addition, the experimental model of physical education has been implemented in the form of "full selection", allowing learners to choose the subjects they like. Create more conditions for learners to improve self-consciousness, volunteer to participate in activities, make sport and physical training activities more effective. To implement the above issues better, it is necessary to have good methods of management, which are strict and consistent with the trend of development and integration. This is a challenge and an urgent requirement of VNU-HCM's leaders.

The following methods of study have been used in this article: Reference Methods and Document Analysis method; Interview method; Sociological investigation method; Statistical methods.

The subject of the study is: the management of physical training and sport resources of Vietnam National University in Ho Chi Minh City.

2. Research Context

2.1. Concepts and Functions of Governance

Definition: Governance is explained in a variety of ways and no definition is accepted by all.

According to management method of Mary Parker Follett (1868-1933), "*Governance is the art of achieving the goal through others.*" This definition implies that executives achieve the goals of the organization by arranging and delegating the work to others rather than completing the work on their own.

James Stoner and Stephen Robbins states that: "*Governance is the process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling the activities of members of the organization and using all other resources of the team. to achieve the set goals*""[4]. The word "process" in this definition states that planning, organizing, managing and controlling must be done in a certain order. The concept also indicates that all executives must carry out management activities to achieve their desired goals.

Governance can be understood as the means, the tricks by which an organization with finite resources that can reach a set goal of the organization.

Here, we also need to understand and to differentiate the terms "management" and "administration":

Management is "*the process of working together and through individuals, groups and other resources (equipment, capital, technology) to achieve the goals of the organization.*"

Administration is the "*process of planning, organizing, leading and inspecting the activities of its members, using resources to achieve success in its goals.*"

Thus, administration in the field of sports and physical training can focus on the following aspects: human resources, equipment and facilities for sports activities.

2.1.1 Functions of Administration

Administration has four main functions including: Planning; Organizing; Managing and Testing.

- Planning is assessing the resources and current status of the organization, identifying goals to achieve, setting action to achieve the goals.
- Organization is creating a favorable internal environment to accomplish the goals, establishing an organizational structure and setting authority for the department, individual, and creating horizontal and vertical coordination in the operation of the organization.
- Managing is leading the human factors so that the organization reaches the goal.
- Checking is evaluating the quality of the implementing process and identifying possible deviations or outlays from the organization's plans.

2.2. The status of Sport Resources in Vietnam

2.2.1. Human Resources

Human resources is manpower in every human being and which makes man active. Sports and physical training personnel includes sport staff management, physical education trainers, coaches, referees, trainees and other services.

Sport management staff: Currently, VNU-HCM does not have specialized managers in physical training and sports, but only in part-time one or people from other management positions overtake the position of management, who still participate in teaching and training physical education in schools.

About lecturers: As a part of education, physical education always exists two main subjects: teachers and students. In a broad sense, teachers in physical education include teachers of physical training (full-time and part-time), coaches, guides; Students

are athletes and voluntary individuals in an organization. Between these two subjects there is always a strong relationship and must be ensured at a rate consistent with the rules of the educational process.

At present, VNU-HCM has a total of 35 lecturers who are teaching and managing physical education sector.

Qualifications of the trainers are also standardized and advanced, in addition to the certificates required by the trainers, the teacher is also self-conscious of learning to improve their knowledge and skill. At present, there are 3 PhD candidates, accounting for 8.6%; There are 6 people who are PhD student, accounting for 17.1% and the rest are masters and master students; No faculty members have college and under-college level (Table 1).

Table 1: Number of staffs, lecturers in VNU-HCM

No	The member universities in Hochiminh National University (VNU-HCM)	Total	Qualifications			
			Dr	PhD student	MSc	MSc student
1	Administration Department	1		1	-	
2	Polytechnic University	5			5	
3	University of Natural Sciences	8	1		5	2
4	University of Social Sciences and Humanities	17	2	3	10	2
5	International University	1		1	-	
6	Information Technology University	0				
7	Economy-Law university	1		1	-	
8	Faculty of Medicine	0				
9	The gifted High school	2			2	
Total:		35	3	6	22	4
Proportion %			8.6%	17.1%	62.9%	11.4%

According to Table 1, only the faculty members of the University of Social Sciences and Humanities (VNU-SIV) have met the required teaching needs of the university. Especially, there are no faculty members for teaching physical education in some universities such as: IT University, Faculty of Medicine, so these universities have to invite teachers of physical education from others schools. This has greatly curtailed the teaching and development of physical training in the school.

The occupational structure of VNU-HCM's staffs and trainers is impacted by age and years of work. Young lecturers, with fewer years of teaching are doing the two tasks as the same time teaching and working as faculty / department secretary. In contrast, older teachers who have longer years of working tend to do management work and teaching at the same time. This trend is relatively common not only in educational institutions but also in other agencies and departments in VNU-HCM in particular and in the country in general.

Table 2: Career structure by age and seniority (n = 35)

Age			Year of working			Title			
Age	Quantity	Proportion	Number of Year	Quantity	Percentage	Manager	Lecturer	Officer	Others
<25	1	2.8	0-5	1	2.8		1		
25-30	5	14.2	6-10	9	25.7		8	1	
31-35	6	17.1	11-15	11	31.4		11		
36-40	8	22.8	16-20	4	11.4	1	4	2	
41-45	5	14.2	21-25	3	8.5	1	4		3
46-50	1	2.8	26-30	3	8.5		3		
51-55	6	17.1	31-35	2	5.7	2	2		1
>55	3	8.5	>35	2	5.7		2		1

The table 2 shows clearly that teachers of the age 36-40 take largest proportion of lecturers, accounting for 22.8%; The lowest proportion is the groups under the age 25 and in the age of 46-50 which has only one, accounting for 2.8%. According to working year, the group of 11-15 accounted for the majority with 11 people, accounting for 31.4% and the lowest is the group of working years from 0-5, only 1, accounting for 2.8% . There are 5 lecturer-manager and lecturers participating in the social organization such as the Football Association, the Volleyball Federation, the national and international competition managers, accounting for 14.2%.

The majors of sports cadres and trainers in VNU-HCM are of the wide varieties, however, there are some majors with small number of teachers, like the chess or shooting ... while others majors have a lot of teachers like volleyball with 17 teacher, accounting for 48.5%. This has made the learning of optional sports unevenly spread, as there are not enough qualified teachers to teach the subjects that students love and the number of teachers is not enough to train the teams for local, national and international competitions.

About the program and the place of training of lecturers: All are studying in the country, accounting for 100%; six gets master degree from foreign country (Taiwan and China), accounting for 17.1%; There is one teacher having PhD degree and one teacher is studying for PhD degree abroad, accounting for 5.7%.

Assessing the suitability of work assigned by professional level: By survey, 35 interviews with VNU-HCM staff and lecturers on the appropriateness of assigned work and other tasks, 74.2% of teachers said it was *“totally appropriate”*, 14.2% said it was *“partly inappropriate”* and only 11.4% said it was *“totally inappropriate”*. The reason for *“totally inappropriate”* is that some teachers admitted to work in the universities but are not assigned to a professional job but are assigned to work as secretary of physical education faculty / department or as an specialist in other departments.

Table 3: Assessment of suitability of assigned tasks (n = 35)

Level	Quantity	Percentage	Work assigned
Totally Appropriate	26	74.2	Teaching
Partly Inappropriate	5	14.2	Teaching and office task
Totally Inappropriate	4	11.4	Doing the task not related to major

2.2.2. Equipment and facilities for sports activities

Equipment and facilities for sports activities are stadiums, fields, court, swimming pool, running track, martial arts training room, the support tools in training and competition etc. In the teaching and learning as well as in the development of sport and physical training in the school, the investment in equipment, tools, and facilities is very important and necessary. Well-managing the equipment is a great contribution to the development of sport movement in VNU-HCM. But in fact, not only in VNU-HCM but almost all schools in the country have very little investment in this field.

In reality, the National University of Ho Chi Minh City, including some member universities, has been investigated for the the yards and pitches serving for physical education as following. The University of Natural Sciences which has the highest total area, of 10,250 m² (in which the school Gymnasium is about 1,250 m² and outdoor training grounds are 9,000 m²). In contrast, the International University has the lowest area of 200 m² (Table tennis practice room). Although the total area is lower, the Polytechnic University and the University of Social Sciences and Humanities have a gymnasium of 1,500 m², which is higher than that of the College of Physical Education of the University of Science, of 1,250 m² (Table 4). To Decision No. 2160 / QD-TTg regulates the area of training ground for physical education and sports in schools at all levels (m² / pupil/ student) as follows: professional and vocational secondary schools, colleges and vocational colleges, universities: must achieve 02 m² /student by 2015, reach 03 m²/student by 2020 and reach 04 m²/student by 2030.

The enrollment of students at the member universities of VNU-HCM is from 2,500 to 3,000 students per year. So many schools do not meet the standard of facilities.

Table 4: Condition of Facilities for Physical Education at VNU-HCM

The member universities in Hochiminh National University (VNU-HCM)	Facility			Demand	Annual budget (million đồng)	
	Total area (m ²)	Gymnasium (m ²)	Outdoor field (m ²)			Capacity
Polytechnic University	4,875	1,500	3,375	95%	Inadequate	100
University of Natural Sciences	10,250	1,250	9,000	80%	Adequate	60
University of Social Sciences and Humanities	2,000	1500	500	80%	Adequate	90
Economy-Law university	500	None	500	20%	Inadequate	10
Information Technology University	1,000	None	1,000	30%	Inadequate	-
International University -	200	Table tennis room		10%	Inadequate	

(1USD=23.300 Vietnam Dong)

In addition, VNU-HCM also has a project to build a VNU-HCM sports complex of (30 hecta) with the total investment of 10,000,000,000 VND (ten billion VND equals 400,000 USD) with 4 mini football fields with artificial grass, 4 volleyball courts, 2 basketball courts, ancillary construction, garage, infrastructure etc. and it is completed in September/2017 but has not been put into use yet. At present, VNU-HCM is constructing the second phase with a total investment of 40,000,000,000 VND (forty billion VND equals 1,600,000 USD) with 01 football field with real grass, 4 football fields with artificial grass, 4 volleyball courts, 2 basketball courts, ancillary works, auxiliary facilities, parking, infrastructure, wastewater treatment station etc.

The cost of investment in equipment and sport facilities of university is not specified. Usually, at the beginning of a school year based on reality, the head of the department will propose facilities needed to the school to buy.

2.2.3. Extracurricular activities and movements in VNU-HCM

In addition to teaching the mainstream courses, every school /department in VNU-HCM held a sport event for the school or the department once a year. sport event of VNU-HCM is held every two years (football, volleyball, table tennis, badminton, chess and chinese chess for both male and female students, lasts about 15 days), to the present time it has held 10 times the Congress of Sports and Games VNU-HCM. This is a very useful and meaningful activity to promote the movement of physical training and sports in students and to search and foster talented athletes to participate in national and international student competitions.

In parallel with the student athletic movement, sports and physical training activities are held once every two years in VNU-HCM and every year, each member school organizes a competition on the major holidays such as Vietnam Teachers' Day on November 20th, the establishment of the school etc. The school also organized a team to participate in major competitions such as the Sport competition in Education, Sport competition organized by the Federation of Labor etc.

In addition, the schools also open sports clubs for extra-curricular activities such as martial arts clubs, volleyball clubs, football, badminton, table tennis ... Thus, creating good conditions for people to participate in training. It contributes to maintain and develop the physical well-being for studying and working.

2.3. Assessing the status of sport management in VNU-HCM

2.3.1. Organizational structure of human resource management

- Board of Directors is an important element in the formation, development and orientation of sports in VNU-HCM in long-term. It has the function of directing the entire operation of VNU-HCM, making decisions and strategies for physical training and sports development in particular as well as all other activities in VNU-HCM in parallel with the development of comprehensive education.
- Student Affairs Department of VNU-HCM: under the direct guidance of VNU-HCM's leaders, in collaboration with other relevant units in charge of sport

activities of students organizes the training, leads the teams competing in national and international competitions, held the VNU-HCM Student Festival of Sport every 2 years etc

- VNU-HCM Trade Union: Under the direct leadership of VNU-HCM's leadership, in conjunction with other departments of the university in charge of physical training and sport activities of all officials and lecturers. In the whole VNU-HCM is also held every 2 years, set up the sports teams for staff to participate in the sport competition of the city, of the education department etc.
- Board of Management of member Universities: VNU-HCM is assigned autonomy and self-determination, but suitable and in accordance with the mechanism of VNU-HCM. This is an important element in the process of formation, development and orientation of sport in Universities.
- Board of Management has the function of directing all activities of the school, making decisions and strategies for sport development in particular as well as all other activities in the school in general.
- Student affair Office: Directly directed by the school's management board, combining with other departments such as Youth Union, Department of Physical Education, others departments and other sports in the school in accordance with the annual plan of the university.
- School Trade Union: Directly directed by the Party Committee, School Management Board, in conjunction with other departments to organize activities and sports competition for all staff in the school.
- Physical Education Department which is directly directed by the Board of Management, Faculty (if sport department is a small section in the faculty), in combination with other units such as Student Affairs Office, Youth Union, Trade Union Office, faculties, and other departments in the school organize all activities for students and staff. Teachers and trainers in physical education department are the core force to participate in consultancy on organization of prize, training of athletes, and running tournaments.
- Youth Union directly directed by the Party Committee, School Management Board, in collaboration with the Student Affairs Office, the Department of Physical Education promotes and develops the sports movement in the school.

Diagram 1: Organizational structure of sport management in VNU-HCM

In this organizational structure, all sports activities of VNU are organized by VNU-HCM Student Union and Student Union in conjunction with other school units. Because of the fact that VNU-HCM does not have human resources for sport and physical training. All staff and trainers and physical training facilities belong to member universities. All the activities and organization of physical training and sport activities of VNU-HCM are managed by VNU-HCM but the member schools will implement the tasks.

2.3.2. Facility management and other assurance conditions

Equipment and infrastructure for physical education is an indispensable condition in every sport and physical activity. According to the above statistics, the current facilities in VNU-HCM is also relatively meet the demand for sports activities in VNU-HCM. These facilities belong to the management and use of the schools, so they have been assigned to various departments to manage and operate, such as the University of Social Sciences and Humanities established the a management board to operate, manage the facilities, the University of Technology is assigned to the Department of Maintenance, and the University of Natural Sciences assigned this task to the Department of physical Education. But no matter which department is managing the facilities. all non-plan activities must be reported to the school head.

2.3.3. Assess the level of satisfaction of human resources when subjected to the impact of governance

The level of human resource satisfaction is one of the most important issues, it reflects the management of the leaders, the regimes and policies for them. Based on the level of satisfaction of human resources, the leaders will have appropriate solutions to improve, develop and attract high quality human resources.

Through the survey, 35 staff members who are currently teaching in VNU-HCM were interviewed on the level of satisfaction during their working time (interviewees can choose many different criteria) In terms of contented with working time, the number was at the highest rate, at 65.7%; On the contrary, the unsatisfied on the current salary level is the highest with 97.1%; In terms of satisfaction, the two criteria "Management of Heads of Units / Units for Sports and Physical Activity" and "Current Activity" take the highest proportion, accounting for 71.4% and lowest The criterion of "Sport development policy of student movement" accounts for 2.8%. But besides that, many interviewees also said that they have no idea, which shows that there is a small group not interested in the organisation and policies as well as sport activities in school. These people just accept the job and trying to accomplish the task assigned is what they want.

Table 5: Assessment of human resource satisfaction (n = 35)

No	Criteria	Level (percentage%)			
		Completely satisfied	Satisfied	Not satisfied	No comments
1	Sports management of VNU-HCM		34.2	28.5	8.5
2	Management of heads of sections / units for sport activities		71.4	14.2	14.2
3	Policies on human resource development and sport development			34.2	42.8
4	policy on attracting talented athletes to VNU			62.8	37.1
5	Policy on investment in development of physical training and sports facilities		8.5	71.4	20.0
6	Sport development policy for the student movement		2.8	65.7	2.8
7	Investment Policy on Sport Development of Employees in VNU		31.4	57.1	11.4
8	Coordination and effective use of sport resources		42.8	42.8	14.2
9	Current job	20.0	71.4	8.5	
10	Current Salary			97.1	2.8
11	Total current income		25.7	74.2	
12	Current policy for talented athletes		14.2	71.4	14.2
13	The job assignment	14.2	54.2	17.1	14.2
14	Working time of the week	65.7	28.5	5.7	
15	the connect between departments in University	40.0	34.2	20.0	5.7
16	the connect between departments in University	20.0	51.4	14.2	14.2
17	Support for sports and physical education activities of school units	14.2	54.2	17.1	14.2
18	the connect between schools in VNU for sports development		25.7	57.1	17.1
19	The interest of school leaders in sports and physical training	11.4	48.5	25.7	14.2

3. Conclusions

The assessment of the actual situation of sport management in VNU-HCM showed that some issues need to be adjusted and improved such as: leaders of VNU-HCM as well as leaders of schools have not paid much attention to the selection and training of high quality human resources; the investment for equipment and infrastructure for sports and physical activity is also uneven and unfocused. There are few schools that invest very little on physical education. There are universities with no facilities for physical education such as University of Economics and Law, International University, University of Information Technology, Faculty of Medicine, University of France etc.; the sport movement in VNU-HCM is also just an outside, it is not invested properly; the management has not really attracted high quality human resources and many of the inadequacies need to be adjusted and reformed. Therefore, the research and assessment of the current situation to find limitations and inadequacies in management is a very important and significant contribution to the sport development of VNU-HCM in particular as well as the schools in the country in general. Based on this situation, there will be further research on solutions to enhance the management capacity, which will help the sports and physical training in VNU-HCM to develop stably and sustainably.

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